

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART II. SEPARATION FROM CERITE EARTHS. *o*-AND *p*-AMINOBENZOIC ACIDS

By D. S. N. MURTHY AND BH. S. V. RAGHAVA RAO

Thorium can be precipitated quantitatively by *o*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids from solutions of p_n 4.2 and more. Rare earths in monazite can be removed by a double precipitation at the same p_n . Interference from other common elements is less in the case of *para*-acid.

In the course of an extended investigation into reagents suitable for the estimation and separation of thorium from rare earths in monazite we have noticed that both *o*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids possess valuable properties (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 487). Sodium anthranilate has been employed by Goto (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1934, 55, 1156) for the precipitation of Zn, Cd, etc., while the ammonium salt has been reported by Shemyakin and Belkon (*Compt. rend. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R.*, 1938, 18, 275; *Chem. Abst.*, 1938, 32, 4470) to give an abundant dark red precipitate with tetravalent cerium. Both *o*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids give voluminous precipitates with thorium, and as small as 1.0 mg. of thoria gives a precipitate sufficient for convenient handling. The *para*-benzoate is more fine and has a greater tendency to become colloidal, but it has the advantage that interference from other metals is much less.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation.—A stock solution of pure thorium nitrate was estimated with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (Neish, *Chem. News*, 1904, 90, 196). 20 ml. of this solution gave 0.1496 g. of ThO_2 . The same was determined with *o*- and *p*-benzoic acids by precipitation from boiling solution in the presence of ammonium acetate yielding the values 0.1496 g. and 0.1498 g. respectively in good agreement therewith.

Separation of Thorium.—Thorium is completely precipitated by both the acids at a p_n of 4.2 and over. Precipitation of other rare earths by these acids occurs at p_n 4.8.

A convenient p_n for the effective removal of the rare earths will be 4.2 to 4.4 which is easily established under the following conditions.

(a) **Single Precipitation: Procedure.**—Make the solution just acid to Congo red and dilute to 10 ml. Add now 5 ml. of 5% ammonium acetate. Boil and add in a steady stream with continuous stirring 75 ml. of a boiling 1% solution of the reagent; continue to boil for 3 minutes, and set aside to cool. Collect the precipitate on Whatmann No. 41 (42 in case of *p*-acid) and wash with 0.1% solution of the precipitant. (Add 1 g. of ammonium acetate for every 250 ml. of wash liquid in the case *p*-acid). Dry, ignite and weigh as ThO_2 .

(b) **Double Precipitation.**—When the rare-earth: thoria ratio is greater than 4:1, procedure will be as follows. Dissolve the precipitate in hot dilute nitric acid, catching the liquid in the original beaker. Adjust the acidity by adding carefully dilute ammonia

and ammonium acetate and repeat the precipitation. Wash, dry and ignite. Results obtained by this procedure are shown in Table I.

Composition of the Precipitate.—It is very interesting to note that the composition of the precipitate is not the same in both cases. While the anthranilates of divalent elements Zn, Cd, etc., are definite compounds and non-hydrated, the thorium compound is different. Ignition tests indicate that thorium anthranilate is anhydrous and in the precipitate two molecules of the acid are associated with one thorium ion, thus pointing to the presence of two hydroxyl groups. Thorium *p*-aminobenzoate on the other hand appears to have a composition in which one acid group is associated with one thorium ion together with 4 molecules of water. This salt then has the probable composition,

where Ac represents the acid group. The composition is not definite in both cases and shows slight variations. Ignition to the oxide is therefore necessary.

TABLE I

Separation of thorium from rare earths.

Admixture		<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid.		<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid.	
Cerite earths.		ThO ₂ found.	Difference.	ThO ₂ found.	Difference.
R ₂ O ₃	0.189 g.	0.1496 g.	-0.2 mg.	0.1495 g.	-0.3 mg.
"	0.30	0.1495	-0.3	0.1497	-0.1
"	0.60	0.1496	-0.2	...	...
"	0.72	0.1497	-0.1	0.1498	0.0
"	1.20	0.1510*	+1.2	0.1508*	+1.0
"	"	0.1498†	0.0	0.1497†	-0.1
"	1.40	0.1520*	+2.2	0.1519‡	+2.1
"	"	0.1497†	-0.1	0.1496†	-0.2
"	1.80	0.1528*	+3.0	0.1530*	+3.2
"	"	0.1495†	-0.3	0.1494†	-0.4

* Single precipitation.

† Double precipitation.

Interferences

(a) *o*-Aminobenzoic acid.—Zr, Ti, Pb, Fe, Ce^{IV}, Al, Cu, Ni, Co., UO₂⁺⁺ and Mn all gave high values of ThO₂ and the impurity persisted even after double precipitation.

(b) *p*-Aminobenzoic acid.—With this reagent there was no interference from a number of common elements viz., Pb, UO₂⁺⁺, Co, Ni, Bi and Mn but Zr, Ce^{IV}, Ti, Cu, and Al co-precipitated and even a double precipitation was not satisfactory. The amount

of impurity added amounted to 0.2 to 0.8 g. calculated to the oxide in every case. In all cases of interference its effect is noticeable even in amounts as small as 0.01 g.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite.—The method was applied to the assay of monazite for thorium. The thorium was determined by double precipitation and the values were compared with those obtained with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (*loc. cit.*). The decomposition of monazite (a sample from Travancore) has been described in an earlier communication (*vide* Part I, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457).

TABLE II

<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.		<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid.		<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid.	
Sample.	ThO ₂ .	Sample.	ThO ₂ .	Sample.	ThO ₂ .
1. 1.0869 g.	8.96%	1. 1.2849 g.	9.00%	1. 1.3052	8.97%
1. 1.2964 g.	9.00	2. 1.6475	8.98	2. 1.0240	8.96
3.		3. 1.7264	8.97	3. 1.5620	8.96
	<u>Mean 8.98</u>		<u>Mean 8.98</u>		<u>Mean 8.97</u>

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
ANDHRA UNIVERSITY,
WALTAIR.

Received April 11, 1950.